

Reversed-phase Extraction Chromatography of Gallium(III) on Silica Gel impregnated with High Molecular Weight Carboxylic Acid

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A novel method has been developed for reversed-phase extraction chromatographic separation of Ga^{III} with Versatic 10 impregnated on silica gel as the stationary phase. Ga^{III} has been extracted in the pH range 3.2–4 from acetic acid and sodium acetate solution and was stripped with 1M hydrochloric acid. Effects of variables such as pH, stripping agents and flow rate on extraction and elution have been studied. Ga^{III} has been separated from a variety of elements present in binary and multicomponent mixtures by exploiting the differences in their extractability or stripping characteristics with different eluents.

HIGH molecular weight carboxylic acid, viz. Versatic 10 has been used for the extraction of gallium(III) and its separation from other associated elements¹. This fact has been utilised to study the extraction chromatographic behaviour of gallium(III) on silica gel impregnated with Versatic 10 and its selective separation.

Experimental

An Elico LI-10 pH meter and chromatographic column (1 × 6 cm) of Borosil glass with a glass-wool plug were used. Versatic 10 (Shell Chemical; a mixture of C₁₀ isomeric tertiary monocarboxylic acid) was used as such. The stock solution of Ga^{III} was prepared by dissolving gallium nitrate (E. Merck; 1 g) in deionised water containing concentrated HNO₃. The solution was standardised complexometrically with EDTA². The diluted solution (containing 1 mg ml⁻¹ Ga^{III}) was prepared by appropriate dilution. Buffer solutions of different pH were prepared by mixing 0.1M acetic acid and 0.1M sodium acetate in proper ratio.

Silica gel (60–120 mesh; B.D.H.) was rendered hydrophobic by exposing it to the vapour of dimethyl dichlorosilane in an atmosphere of nitrogen for 5 h³, then washed with methanol and dried at 100°. 1 ml of dimethyl dichlorosilane was found to be adequate for 10 g of silica gel. 1 g of gel could take up about 0.8 ml of Versatic 10. The gel was coated by treating with a benzene solution of Versatic 10 and evaporated on rotary vacuum evaporator to have a uniform coating. Coated silica gel (4 g) was slurried with water and poured into the column. The bed was washed with 1M HCl to remove excess of organic solvent. Silica gel was found suitable for the support for being porous and able to retain a considerable amount of

the exchanger. Each column, prepared in this way, was suitable for at least 40 cycles without any loss of exchange capacity.

General procedure: The acetate buffer (10 ml) of pH 3.2 containing 1 mg Ga^{III}, was passed through the coated silica gel column at a flow rate 1 ml min⁻¹. The pH of the column was adjusted to 3.2 before passing the metal ion in each operation. This was done by washing the column with acetate buffer of pH 3.2. The effluent was collected in different fractions and estimated complexometrically.

Results and Discussion

Effect of pH: Extraction of Ga^{III} was performed at various pH taking 1 mg of Ga. Results show that the extraction of Ga increased with the increase in pH and becomes quantitative at pH 3.2–4.0. Ga^{III} undergoes hydrolysis at pH > 4, hence extraction studies at higher pH were not performed.

Stripping agent: Hydrochloric acid, nitric acid, sulphuric acid, sodium chloride and potassium chloride were tested as the stripping agent⁴. Elution of Ga^{III} was quantitative with 1M hydrochloric acid and 1M nitric acid. Sulphuric acid was also a good stripping agent but it seriously interfered in the estimation of Ga^{III}, whereas salts like sodium chloride and potassium chloride were found to be poor eluting agents. Therefore 1M hydrochloric acid was preferred as the stripping agent for all practical purposes.

Separation of Ga^{III} from binary mixture: It was possible to separate Ga^{III} from several binary mixture by exploiting the differences in pH at which

they formed acetato complex. At pH 3.2, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II}, Cr^{III}, Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Ti^{IV}, La^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III}, Gd^{III}, Dy^{III} and U^{VI} did not form acetato complex, therefore they passed through the column whereas Ga^{III} was held up, then Ga^{III} was stripped quantitatively with 1M hydrochloric acid. Al^{III}, Zn^{II} and In^{III} were quantitatively extracted along with Ga^{III} but Al^{III} and Zn^{II} were stripped with water and with 0.01M hydrochloric acid. Zr^{IV}, Th^{IV} and Fe^{III} were co-extracted with Ga^{III}, causing interference.

Separation of Ga^{III} from multicomponent mixture : The proposed method has been applied to separate Ga^{III} from groups of elements which are also extractable with Versatic 10, by exploiting the differences in stripping behaviour. Different concentration of hydrochloric acid were used for selective stripping. Metal ions not sorbed on the column passed through with the mobile phase.

Separation of Ga^{III} from In^{III} and Ti^{IV} : At pH 3.2 (acetate buffer). Ga^{III}, In^{III} and Ti^{IV} were passed on the column, when Ga and In were extracted quantitatively but Ti^{IV} passed through the column. In^{III} was eluted with 0.01M hydrochloric acid and finally Ga^{III} was eluted with 1M hydrochloric acid.

Separation of Ga^{III} from Y^{III} and La^{III} : At pH 3.2 (acetate buffer), Ga^{III}, Y^{III} and La^{III} solution was passed on the column, when Y and La passed through but gallium was extracted. Ga^{III} was eluted quantitatively with 1M hydrochloric acid.

Separation of Ga^{III} from Zn^{II} and Mn^{II} : Ga^{III}, Zn^{II} and Mn^{II} solution in acetate buffer of pH 3.2 was passed on the column, when Ga and Zn were extracted whereas Mn passed through the column. Zn^{II} was eluted quantitatively with water followed by the elution of Ga^{III} with 1M hydrochloric acid.

Separation of Ga^{III} from Al^{III}, In^{III} and Ti^{IV} : Al^{III}, Ga^{III}, In^{III} and Ti^{IV} solution in acetate buffer of pH 3.2 was passed through the column. Ga, Al and In were extracted but Ti^{IV} passed through the column. Al^{III} from the column was eluted quantitatively with water, In^{III} was eluted with 1M hydrochloric acid. Elution behaviour of Ga^{III} from multicomponent mixtures is given in Fig. 1 and the results for extractive separation are given in Table 1. The separation of Ga^{III} from rare earth elements involving separation and estimation is possible within 2 h.

Fig. 1. Separation of Ga^{III} from multicomponent mixtures.

TABLE 1 - SEPARATION OF Ga^{III} FROM MULTICOMPONENT MIXTURES*

Metal ions	Taken mg	Found mg	Recovery %	Eluent (HCl) M
Ti ^{IV}	1.9	1.92	101.0	-
In ^{III}	1.9	1.88	98.9	0.01
Ga ^{III}	1.0	1.02	102.0	2.0
La ^{III}	1.3	-	-	-
Y ^{III}	1.0	-	-	-
Ga ^{III}	1.0	0.98	98.0	1
Mn ^{II}	2.5	2.47	98.8	-
Zn ^{II}	2.0	2.02	101.0	H ₂ O
Ga ^{III}	1.0	0.99	99.0	1.0
Ti ^{IV}	1.9	1.89	99.4	-
Al ^{III}	2.0	2.01	101.5	H ₂ O
In ^{III}	1.9	1.91	100.5	0.01
Ga ^{III}	1.0	.99	99.0	1.0

*Flow rate = ml min⁻¹ ; exchanger taken = 4 g.

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